

History & Future of consumption habits in Austria

Fabian Feyersinger
Österreich
6305 Itter
fabi.feyersinger@gmail.com

Abstract

This paper is determined to show off the efforts of working with three Kaggle datasets. It should also act as an assignment for the subject Data Science for Natural Science at the FH Kufstein Tirol.

The three datasets all include different information gathered by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) and are considered to be of high quality. Dataset number one contains details about Crop Statistics of all countries. Furthermore, it includes the population of all countries. Dataset number two holds data about the consumption of grown food. Lastly there is a file about the global emission from agriculture and forest land.

Keywords

Data Science, Data analysis, Social Science, Kaggle, Python, Jupyter, emission, consumption, population, agriculture, Austria

1. Introduction

The year 2022 just started and people in Europe seem to care more and more about what they eat. According to a statistic by statista.de is Austria the country with the highest meat consumption throughout the EU. Nonetheless, the percentage of vegetarians and flexitarians is increasing steadily. Within four years they were able to record a growth of 4%. In 2021 there are 11% of Austrians indicating to be vegetarian. (Schultz, 2017)

Even though this number seems promising, several questions persist: Is there a visible reduction in meat consumption and an increase in other foods? Is there a correlation between agricultural emissions and consumption habits? Following the current trend can we forecast future consumption habits? This paper should offer a starting point for these questions.

2. Population

Starting off with the smallest dataset, it is clear that the population in Austria is increasing steadily since the start of recording in 1950. The file contains several columns including the total population (thousands), male population (thousands), female population (thousands) and population density. An explorative data analysis showed that there is no difference between the male and female numbers. Those charts look exactly like the one below shown in figure 1. Interestingly, the source provides several predictions till 2100. Realistically, all variants forecasting a decrease of population can probably be discarded, subject to the condition that there will be no war, economical or environmental crisis. That said, an increase will most likely look like either "High", "Instant replacement" or "Upper 95 PI" prediction.

Figure 1: Population of Austria

3. Consumption

This dataset was uploaded to Kaggle 4 years ago and contains information about the worldwide food/feed production and distribution from 1961 till 2013. More precisely, it presents a comprehensive picture of a country's food supply during a specified reference period. (From Content description of dataset) There are two main chunks. Food refers to the total amount of the food item available to humans. Feed refers to the quantity of the food item available to animals. As this paper lays its focus on Austria there are several items that can be discarded. During a feature selection several items of interest distilled. Those are:

Figure 2: Consumption of Austria - Relevant Items

"Wheat and products", "Barley and products",
"Maize and products", "Rye and products", "Oats",
"Potatoes and products", "Sugar (Raw Equivalent)",
"Vegetables, Other", "Oranges, Mandarines",
"Apples and products", "Fruits, Other", "Wine",

"Beer", "Bovine Meat", "Pigmeat", "Poultry Meat",
 "Milk - Excluding Butter", "Cereals - Excluding Beer",
 "Starchy Roots", "Vegetables", "Fruits - Excluding Wine", "Meat"
 As figure 2 still seems messy the data will be divided into the two major chunks Food and Feed.

3.1 Feed

Looking at Figure 3, it is visible that the habits of feeding changed in recent times.

Figure 3: Feeding in Austria - Summary Items

Back in 1960 starchy roots were the main component in livestock dishes. Knowing Austria as a country explains that those are almost exclusively potatoes. In 1970 Cereals surpassed starchy roots as most fed item. Modern farming is often trimmed to achieve high productivity. Therefore, a mix of cereals called concentrate ("Kraftfutter" in German) is used, as they offer the most energy. Milk feeding used to be more popular in the 20th century but has decreased since 1985. Later on there will be a comparison between food and feed consumption in milk explaining this occurrence.

Fish is an interesting factor when it comes to feeding. According to an article from 2009, 36% of caught fish was fed to livestock. This sounds alarmingly high, but it is not really the case in Austria. Fishmeal, oils and fish were used to feed pigs and poultry in earlier times, but those numbers washed out over time and now make only a minimal percent of feed. (Hance, 2009)

3.1.1 Cereals and Crops

As Cereals is the most fed category it is worth to dig deeper into it. Splitting up the category into its components and plotting them shows an interesting fact. To strengthen the assumption that starchy roots contain mainly from potatoes, those will be added to figure 4 as well.

Comparing the starchy roots line of figure 3 and the potatoes and products line in figure 4, the similarities in characteristics are in evidence. Maize and barley used to be similar until 1997 where the use of barley slumped down. In general, these numbers represent the often-used mixtures of concentrate.

Figure 4: Feeding in Austria - Cereals and Crops

3.2 Food

In comparison to feed the food is more balanced between the major types of items. As figure 5 shows, milk is the most consumed food item. Even after a great depression in 2002 the milk consume is still on top. All other categories, except fish, are balanced. Starchy roots, that mostly consist of potatoes, stayed the same since 1961. Alcoholic Beverages does have two main items: Beer and wine and only slightly increased during the last 50 years.

Figure 5: Food Consumption Austria - Summary Items

Meat, cereals, fruits and vegetables will be discussed in greater detail, as the different components of those categories are alluring.

3.2.1 Meat

Figure 6: Food Consumption Austria - Meat

Looks like meat is still on the menu but not as often as it used to be. Especially pork/pig meat seems to be vacant since its drop back in 1994 yet is the most consumed meat in 2013. Figure 6 also shows that bovine meat (ex. beef) stayed the same within the last 50 years. Only the consume of poultry increases steadily since the start of recording.

3.2.2 Cereals

Completely different to the cereals that are feed to livestock barley and maize do not seem to be popular with humans. Maize especially only increased in 1994 where the imports of popcorn maize got more popular. Rye and products seem to be in a steady decline since 1961. Wheat and potatoes on the other hand are recovering from their small depression during 80s. An explanation for the high values could be that wheat and potatoes are common in Austrian dishes.

Figure 7: Food Consumption Austria - Cereals

3.2.3 Fruits and Vegetables

The most common vegetables in Austria are tomatoes and carrots, followed by lettuce. (Spectra, 2022) Only tomatoes do have their own item slot. The others are grouped as “Vegetables, Other”. This is a misfortune as it could be interesting to compare the consumed amounts. Nevertheless, tomatoes are growing more popular as the consumption more than tripled in the last 50 years.

Figure 8: Food Consumption Austria - Fruits and Vegetables

Fruits are on the rise as well. Apples and others always were popular as most of them can be grown in Austria. Oranges and mandarins reached an enormous peak in 1995 followed by a steep fall. Since 1961 this is the most volatile item.

3.3 Milk

As announced previously milk is a compelling item. As Austria produces enough milk to sustain itself it is possible to conclude that an increase or decrease in food consumption impacts the feed consumption.

Figure 9: Milk consumption Austria

This assumption is supported by the graph in figure 9. Everytime the human consumption of milk decreased sharply; the animals were fed more milk. This is a correlation that is comprehensible and obvious.

4. Consumption per capita

To include some more information on the consumption behavior of Austrian citizens the population size should be considered. In figures 10, 11 and 12 it is shown that the right graph is value divided by the total population in Austria. Comparing this graph with the graph containing the total values shows the value per capita. To show off the real change the first abbreviation should be considered, but this way it is more clearly to look at.

Figure 10: Comparison Meat consumption

When it comes to meat, the consumption per head is slightly reducing. Pork is still the most consumed item per head but also reduces faster than the total consumption. Same habits can be found in the other meat types. For the other items, the differences between total value and value per capita were only marginal.

5. Future consumption habits

To include some type of future insights, a forecasting model was used in order to predict the consumption up to the year 2030. Considering that the last year of the data is 2013 this concludes in a prediction of 17 years. The model, that was used, is called ARIMA and is very popular among data scientists when it comes to timeseries forecasting.

Figure 11: Prediction Meat consumption per head

Figure 11 shows the prediction of meat consume. Especially poultry and bovine meat seem to follow their already existing trend and will continue to rise / fall. Pigmeat seems to level out and maybe even start to increase again in late 2030.

Figure 12: Prediction Fruit/Vegetable consumption per head

Figure 12 shows the trends of fruit and vegetable consumption. With those predictions it is better to see, that the prediction is already a little off in the years 2012 and 2013. Those years were also predicted, so it is possible to compare the predictions with the actual values. Trendwise, there are no surprises in terms of increase and decrease of consumption.

6. Conclusion

Consumption habits come and go but there are clear trends to see when taking a closer look. Meat is still very popular among Austrians and will be in the future. Even if the consumption per head is reducing in recent times, there is no guarantee that this trend continues.

7. Figure reference

- Figure 1: Population of Austria 1
- Figure 2: Consumption of Austria - Relevant Items..... 1
- Figure 3: Feeding in Austria - Summary Items 2
- Figure 4: Feeding in Austria - Cereals and Crops 2
- Figure 5: Food Consumption Austria - Summary Items 2
- Figure 6: Food Consumption Austria - Meat..... 2
- Figure 7: Food Consumption Austria - Cereals..... 3
- Figure 8: Food Consumption Austria - Fruits and Vegetables..... 3
- Figure 9: Milk consumption Austria 3
- Figure 10: Comparison Meat consumption..... 3
- Figure 11: Prediction Meat consumption per head..... 4
- Figure 12: Prediction Fruit/Vegetable consumption per head..... 4

8. References

Hance, J. (07. 01 2022). *Mongabay*. Von Mongabay: <https://news.mongabay.com/2009/11/using-fish-as-livestock-feed-threatens-global-fisheries/> abgerufen

Schultz, E. (07. 01 2022). *Statista*. Von Statista: <https://de.statista.com/themen/3804/vegetarismus-und-veganismus-in-oesterreich/> abgerufen

Spectra. (07. 01 2022). *Spectra*. Von Spectra: <https://www.spectra.at/aktuelles/details/obst-und-gemuese-konsum-in-oesterreich.html> abgerufen